

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE INFLUENCE OF GENDER RELATIONS IN THE FAMILY ON THE ADOLESCENT'S COMMUNICATION WITH THE OPPOSITE SEX

Umida Sariboyeva

Tashkent University of Applied Sciences
Candidate of Psychology, Associate Professor

Abdujalilova Sarvinoz Rajjaboyeva Feride
students of Tashkent University of Applied Sciences

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada oiladagi gender munosabatlarining o'smirlarning qarama-qarshi jins bilan muloqot madaniyati va psixologik rivojlanishiga ta'siri yoritilgan. Oiladagi tarbiya uslubi, ota-onalar o'rtasidagi munosabat hamda gender stereotiplarning o'smir shaxsining ijtimoiylashuv jarayoniga ta'siri tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: gender munosabatlari, o'smir psixologiyasi, oilaviy tarbiya, muloqot, ijtimoiylashuv, gender stereotiplari.

Annotation. This article examines the socio-psychological impact of family gender relations on adolescents' communication with the opposite sex. The influence of parenting style, parental relationships, and gender stereotypes on adolescent socialization and interpersonal communication skills is analyzed in the study.

Keywords: gender relations, adolescent psychology, family upbringing, communication, socialization, gender stereotypes.

The role of the family in the development of society is incomparable, it is the first socialization environment of a person. Especially during adolescence, the psychological environment and gender relations in the family have a strong impact on the development of the individual. The way adolescents communicate with the opposite sex, behave and form social relationships is largely related to the style of upbringing in the family. Mutual respect between parents, a culture of communication and the correct distribution of gender roles contribute to the formation of healthy psychological views in children[2].

In today's era of globalization, the widespread use of mass media and the Internet has a significant impact on the worldview and social behavior of adolescents. In such conditions, gender relations in the family take on even greater importance. If there is a conflict environment, discrimination or incorrect gender stereotypes in the family, this can lead to the emergence of insecurity, shyness or aggressiveness in adolescents' communication with the opposite sex. Therefore, studying this topic from a socio-psychological perspective is one of the most pressing scientific issues.

Gender relations in the family are one of the most important socio-psychological factors in the formation of the adolescent's personality. The family is the child's first social environment, where he learns the roles of men and women, the culture of communication, the principles of mutual respect and cooperation. It is at this stage that the views formed later become the main psychological model in the adolescent's relations with the opposite sex[1].

The positive or negative appearance of gender relations in the family directly affects the emotional development of the adolescent. For example, a respectful relationship between father and mother, an atmosphere of equality and cooperation form healthy views of the opposite sex in the child. Adolescents who grow up in such a family are usually confident, open to communication and socially flexible. On the contrary, if conflict situations, discrimination or the dominance of gender stereotypes are observed in the family, this can create psychological barriers in the adolescent.

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Adolescence is a psychologically complex stage, during which a person experiences a process of self-awareness, the formation of their sexual identity, and the acquisition of social roles. In this process, gender relations in the family serve as an important guiding factor. Adolescents form future relationship models by observing the interaction of their parents. If the roles of men and women in the family are complementary and equal, this helps the adolescent to establish healthy relationships with the opposite sex[4].

The psychological aspect of the family environment is also of great importance. In families where there is emotional support, trust, and open communication, adolescents learn to express their thoughts freely. This increases their social competence and reduces insecurity in communicating with the opposite sex. Conversely, a cold or aggressive family environment can increase introversion, shyness, and social fear in adolescents.

Gender stereotypes also have a significant impact on adolescent psychology. For example, rigid views such as “a man should be strong,” and “a woman should be gentle” prevent adolescents from communicating freely. As a result of such stereotypes, boys may hide their emotions, and girls may hesitate to express their opinions openly. This complicates natural and healthy communication with the opposite sex[3].

Also, the communicative culture in the family plays an important role in the formation of a teenager’s social skills. When parents talk openly with their children and patiently answer their questions, a teenager’s sense of trust increases. This trust, in turn, later serves as an important psychological foundation for communicating with peers, including representatives of the opposite sex.

The presence of the principles of gender equality in the family broadens the social views of adolescents. In such families, children learn to evaluate people not by gender, but by their personal qualities. This prevents the formation of discriminatory views and contributes to the development of healthy social relationships[2].

In addition, the media also influences a teenager's communication with the opposite sex. However, strong gender education in the family can balance this influence. If the right values are formed in the family, the teenager will have the ability to critically evaluate the flow of external information.

Social and psychological studies show that adolescents with positive gender relations in the family are more open and empathetic in communication with their peers. They are guided by the principles of respect, understanding and cooperation in their relationships with the opposite sex. This also has a positive effect on their future family life.

At the same time, a negative gender environment in the family can cause a number of psychological problems in a teenager. For example, low self-esteem, social fear, aggression or insecurity make communication with the opposite sex difficult. Such situations also have a negative impact on the social adaptation of the individual[5].

In conclusion, gender relations in the family have a direct and profound socio-psychological impact on the communication of the adolescent with the opposite sex. A healthy family environment, relationships based on equality and respect, form positive communication skills in the adolescent. On the contrary, incorrect gender stereotypes and a conflict environment make social adaptation difficult. Therefore, the development of gender culture in the family is of great importance for the future social stability of society.

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